

Salt crystal deposition as a reversible mechanism to enhance photoprotection in black mangrove

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Abstract

Mangrove forests are ecosystems made up by several woody plants living in saline coastal sedimentary habitats. In order to deal with the high salinity of the substrate, mangrove trees possess a number of different mechanisms to exclude, sequester or excrete the excess of salt. The black mangrove (*Avicennia germinans* L.), one of the dominant species in Central America, is characterised by high levels of salt excretion through epidermal glands. In this study, our aim was to examine whether, apart from its obvious role in salt tolerance, the formation of salt crystals on the upper leaf surface of black mangrove might represent an unusual and dynamic photoprotection mechanism. For this purpose, the reflection of light and a number of physiological parameters were studied during the dry and rainy seasons in black mangroves growing in the Juan Venado Island Nature Reserve (Nicaragua). Excreted salt increased the reflectance of the leaf surface mainly in the blue and red regions of the spectrum. By removing salt crust from the leaf surface, we demonstrated that during the most stressful periods (dry season at noon), this feature allowed leaves to maintain a higher photochemical efficiency and a lower leaf temperature as compared to uncovered leaves. Furthermore, this mechanism is fully reversible when conditions become more favourable, as salt crystals dissolve, forming drops. Thus, while being a detoxification mechanism developed mainly to avoid osmotic imbalance in the tissues, the excretion of salt through the leaves in black mangroves is an example of “exaptation”, as it has positive collateral effects on the photosynthetic performance of the plant, protecting *A. germinans* from overheating and from photodamage during the harsher periods.

Key-words: *Avicennia*, exaptation, mangrove, reflectance, pigments.

Abbreviations: α -toc: α -tocopherol; Chl a+b: total chlorophyll; Chl a/b: chlorophyll a to chlorophyll b; ratio Fv/Fm: maximal photochemical efficiency of PSII; γ - toc chl: γ - tocopherol; JVR: Juan Venado Island Nature Reserve; HS-leaves: half leaves with salt deposition on the adaxial surface; HWS-leaves: half leaves without salt deposition on the adaxial surface; Δ leaf T°: increased leaf temperature; L: lutein; N: neoxanthin; Pi_Abs: performance index on absorbance basis; PRI: photochemical reflectance index; Reflec: % of total reflectance; V: violaxanthin; V+A+Z: total pigments of violaxanthin cycle.

Introduction

Mangrove forests are distributed worldwide on tropical and subtropical shores (Lüttge 1997). Several tree species co-exist in this environment and display different strategies to cope with salinity. One of the most conspicuous mechanisms is shown by the trees of the genus *Avicennia* (black or grey mangrove) whose leaves excrete the salt that has not been excluded by roots (Scholander et al. 1962, Drennan and Pammenter 1982), through specialized glands located in the epidermis (Lüttge 1997). Both the upper and lower part of the leaves present glands, which are more concentrated in adaxial surfaces (Suarez and Medina 2008). Salt ions are accumulated in the leaf hypodermis and are excreted afterwards (Waisel et al. 1986; Smith et al. 1989; Balsamo and Thomson 1993) by a process involving high ATPase activity (Drennan et al. 1982). During the night and early morning, salt excretion is more active (Naidoo 2010). Whenever relative humidity is high, excreted salt absorbs water hygroscopically and leaves are covered by salty water drops. On sunny days, when relative humidity decreases at noon and the water evaporates, the adaxial side of leaves turns whitish because of the formation of salt crystals. The crystals dissolve again at the end of the day (the authors' personal observation). This daily cycle of crystal formation matches the changes in other environmental conditions affecting leaf function. In fact, a side-effect of this process of crystal formation may be the generation of changes in the optical properties of leaves.

As mangrove ecosystems are exposed to strong light and saline conditions give rise to low stomatal conductance and photosynthetic rates (Ball 1988), these ecosystems are particularly prone to photoinhibition (Lovelock and Clough 1992). Thus, it has been shown that photoprotection is an essential feature for the acclimation of mangrove species to the intertidal environment (Christian 2005; Lovelock and Clough 1992). In the present study, we hypothesise that, apart from its role on salinity tolerance, reversible crystal formation also enhances photoprotection through a flexible increase in leaf reflectance (and a consequent decrease in leaf absorbance) during periods of higher photoprotective demand. The strategy of reducing light interception by leaves is ubiquitous in the plant kingdom and it can be achieved in different ways, such as changes in leaf orientation (Lovelock and Clough 1992), leaf rolling (Pastenes et al. 2004), chloroplast movements (Kashahara et al. 2002) or the presence of reflective structures such as waxes (Robinson et al. 1993), hairs or scales (Morales et al. 2002) and crystals (Mooney et al. 1977). Among these mechanisms, chloroplast or leaf movements are dynamic, allowing leaves to adapt flexibly to their environment, but the presence of reflective structures is hardly reversible (Bjorkman and Demmig-Adams 1994). In this study, our aim was to examine whether, apart from its

obvious role in salt tolerance, the formation of salt crystals on the leaf surface of black mangrove (*Avicennia germinans* L.) plants might represent an unusual and dynamic photoprotective mechanism.

Materials And Methods,

Study species, study area and sampling

The field study was carried out in the Juan Venado Island Nature Reserve (JVR) (Nicaragua) (12°22' N, 87°01' W). The climate in JVR is tropical and characterized by a strong seasonality on rainfall distribution (wet and dry seasons). For more climate details see **figure 1** and explanations in results section. The black mangrove is one of the species of the JVR, which characteristically excretes salt by the specialised glands on both sides of the leaves (**Fig. 2**). This deposition of salt forms a salt crystal cover in the adaxial side of the leaf, being more noticeable during the dry season (authors' personal observation). Ten different individuals growing in open sites were selected for the study and the experiments were performed in both dry (November 2009 and November 2011) and wet seasons (July-August 2009 and July-August 2011). For each individual one leaf was randomly selected in order to perform all the measurements (fluorescence, reflectance, leaf temperature and pigment and tocopherol composition; see detailed information below). Salt was gently removed before dawn with a tissue from the left half of the adaxial face of each leaf. This step was repeated every time leaves started to turn whitish over the day course. Throughout the manuscript, each half, intact (with salt) and without salt are stated as HS and HWS, respectively. Both parts were compared during the course of a typical day in each season at predawn (06:00), noon (11:30), afternoon (15:00) and predawn of the next day (06:00).

Leaf discs for chemical analysis were collected and stored as described in Esteban et al. (2009) in paper envelopes filled with silica gel. The samples were transported to the analytical laboratory (UPV/EHU laboratory, Basque Country, Spain) one week later and frozen immediately in liquid nitrogen until analyses. This alternative and suitable method is for preservation of photosynthetic pigments and tocopherols from remote locations, such as JVR, where liquid nitrogen is not available. It provides reliable results, however it possesses the limitation that de-epoxidation index cannot be determined in samples, as there is a residual zeaxanthin formation during the process of preservation (for more detail information see Esteban et al. 2009).

Climatic conditions

Climatic data were recorded from November 2010 to November 2011 by an automatic weather station (MiniCube VV/VX16, EMS, Brno, CZ) close-by the sampling site. Daily quantum flux density (EMS12, EMS,

Brno, CZ), daily rainfall (MetOne370/376, EMS, Brno, CZ) air temperature and relative humidity (EMS33, EMS, Brno, CZ) were monitored along a year course. Data loggers were programmed to record 1-hour averages of environmental measurements taken every minute from November 2010 to November 2011.

Leaf optical properties

Leaf Photochemical Reflectance Index (PRI) was measured in the field during the day course at noon in the dry season (November 2008) with a PRI-meter (PlantPen PRI 200, PSI, Brno, Czech) in the adaxial and abaxial side of HS- and HWS-leaves. This index was calculated as $(R570 - R531)/(R531 + R570)$. On the other hand, thirty four leaf samples were collected from the field in the dry season (April 2010) and measured leaf reflectance in the laboratory before and after salt removing. Leaf reflectance, defined as the proportion of incident light that is reflected from the leaf, was measured with a spectroradiometer (UNISPEC™, FieldSpec UV/NIR portable spectral system, PP Systems, Amesbury, USA) with the optic fiber, leaf-clip holder and reference provided by the manufacturer. Illumination was provided by a light source supplied with an integral 7.0W halogen lamp.

Chlorophyll *a* fluorescence

Chlorophyll *a* fluorescence was determined with a portable chlorophyll fluorimeter (Fluorpen FP100, PSI, Brno, Czech Republic) on dark adapted leaves for minimum of 20 minutes to allow the complete relaxation or oxidation of reaction centres in order to determine basal fluorescence (F_0). Then a saturation pulse of 3000 $\mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ was applied to determine the maximal fluorescence (F_m). The maximal photochemical efficiency of PSII was estimated by the ratio $F_v/F_m = (F_m - F_0)/F_m$ according to Genty et al. (1989). Chlorophyll fluorescence transients were induced by a saturating light of 3000 $\mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$, and fluorescence was recorded during 2 s at a frequency of 10 μs , 100 μs , 1 ms and 10 ms for the time intervals of 10-600 μs , 0.6-14 ms, 14-100 ms and 0.1-2 s, respectively. The fluorescence values at 40 μs (F_0 , step 0), 100 μs (F_{100}), 300 μs (F_{300}), 2ms (step J), 30 ms (step I) and maximal (F_M , step P) were taken into consideration. Cardinal points of the OJIP curve and derived parameters were calculated with the fluorpen 2.0 software, based on the formulas derived from Strasser et al. (2000; 2004) and they were represented in a spider plot together with other physiological characters (**Fig. 5**). The derived parameters were: V_j , relative fluorescence at 2 ms, defined as $(F_j - F_0)/(F_M - F_0)$; V_i , relative fluorescence at 30 ms, defined as $(F_i - F_0)/(F_M - F_0)$; and P_i Abs, which is the performance index (potential) for energy conservation from photons absorbed by PSII to the reduction of

intersystem electron acceptors: $Pi_Abs = [RC/ABS][TR_0/(ABS-TR_0)][ET_0/(TR_0-ET_0)]$. The performance index is derived according to the principles of the Nernst equation for Red-Ox reactions (for more detail of this parameter see Strasser et al. 2000; 2004).

Leaf temperature

Leaf temperature was measured at noon with a digital thermocouple type K (Thandar, TH302) in the adaxial and abaxial side of HS- and HWS-leaves (gently removed as it is explained above). The parameter of increase leaf temperature (Δ leaf T° ; **Fig. 5**) was calculated as the temperature difference between the adaxial and the abaxial sides. Direct heating of thermocouples by direct sunlight could affect the precision of measurements, so Δ leaf T° is only valid for comparative purposes between HS- and HWS-leaves.

Analytical methods

Photoprotective compounds were extracted by grinding leaves in a cooled mortar with a pestle, with 1 ml of acetone (100%) with 0.5 g/l of $CaCO_3$, in order to avoid acid traces which could alter pigment composition. Samples were centrifuged at 13200 rpm for 20 minutes at $4^\circ C$ and syringe-filtered through a $0.22 \mu m$ PTFE filter (Whatman, Maidstone, UK). Extracts were injected (15 μl) in a reverse-phase Waters (Milford, MA, USA) HPLC system following the method of García-Plazaola and Becerril (1999) with some modifications (García-Plazaola and Becerril 2001; García-Plazaola and Esteban 2011). The 717 plus autosampler was equipped with a thermostat which maintains temperature constant at $4^\circ C$ avoiding pigment alteration. Photosynthetic pigments were measured with a PDA detector (Waters model 996) in the range 250-700 nm. Peaks were detected and integrated at 445 nm for carotenoid and chlorophyll content. Pigments were identified and quantified according to García-Plazaola and Becerril (1999). Retention times and conversion factors for pigments were the same as described by García-Plazaola and Becerril (1999; 2001). For tocopherols, detection was carried out with a fluorescence detector (Waters model 474) set to $\lambda_{exc} = 295$ nm and $\lambda_{em} = 340$ nm and calibrated with tocopherol standards (Calbiochem, San Diego, CA).

Statistics

We used a paired t-Student test in order to test differences in photochemical efficiency (**Fig. 4**) and PRI (Table 1). In order to test differences in reflectance (**Fig. 3**) and in pigments and tocopherols (Table 2) one way

Analyses of Variance (ANOVAs) were performed, considering with- and without-salt as a fixed factor. All data were tested for normality and homogeneity of variances and square root- or log-transformed, if necessary. Student–Newman–Keul tests were used to discriminate among different treatments after significant F-test and Cochran’s test to test for heterogeneity of variances. In the case of α -tocopherol one data was replaced by the mean of the group and 1 df subtracted from Residual (Winer et al. 1991), in order to standardize variances. All statistical analyses were performed using SPSS 19.0 statistical package.

Results

Meteorological characterization of JVR

The meteorological conditions of JVR were monitored during a whole year (November 2010–November 2011). As shown in **figure 1**, thermal seasonality was low, with mean daily temperatures ranging between 25°C and 30°C over the whole year (**Fig. 1a**). Contrasting with temperature, precipitation was unevenly distributed with a marked dry season from December to May in which the total accumulated rainfall was below 4.2 mm (**Fig. 1b**). Along with this dry season, air humidity dropped considerably to values between 50 and 80% (**Fig. 1b**). Daily-accumulated radiation was high throughout the year ($\sim 40 \text{ mol m}^{-2}\text{day}^{-1}$) but was much more variable in the wet season (**Fig.1a**) due to variable amounts of cloud.

Effects of salt crystal deposition on photosynthetic parameters

Salt accumulation on the leaf surface of black mangroves strongly affected the reflectance spectrum over the PAR range (400–700 nm) (**Fig. 3**). Indeed, significant differences were found in the blue (420–500 nm) and red (630–680 nm) regions of the spectrum when HS- and HWS-leaves (see materials and methods) were compared. The reflection of light in these regions of the spectrum may have direct effects on the absorption of light by chlorophylls and consequently on the photosynthetic performance. Thus, the maximal photochemical efficiency of PSII (Fv/Fm) was monitored throughout a typical day of both wet and dry seasons (**Fig. 4**). In the wet season no significant difference was observed in photochemical efficiency between HS and HWS (**Fig. 4a**). However, in the dry season, when crystal deposition was more conspicuous, the HS showed higher photochemical efficiency during the afternoon than the HWS (**Fig. 4b**), indicating a possible photoinhibition of exposed tissues. Additional evidence of this photoinhibition was obtained when the effect of epicuticular salt accumulation on the photochemical reflectance index (PRI) of leaves was analyzed both in the rainy and dry seasons (Table 1).

Particularly in the latter, a considerable decrease in the PRI was observed after salt removal. Thus, HS showed a tendency to present higher PRI values, which indicates that more photons were being used for photochemistry.

Finally, photosynthetic pigment and tocopherol composition was analyzed in the wet and dry season in HS and HWS. Interestingly, the ratios to chlorophyll of α -tocopherol (α -toc) and γ -tocopherol (γ -toc) and of total pigments of violaxanthin (V)-cycle (V+A+Z) differed between seasons, with the first being higher in the wet period and the latter in the dry season (table 2). No significant differences were observed in any parameter between HS- and HWS-leaves.

In order to visualize clearly what was happening in the leaves, a number of physiological parameters of *A. germinans* were depicted in a radar plot presentation (**Fig. 5**). This is a multiparametric description of the structure and function of each photosynthetic sample, represented by a heptagonal line. This type of presentation provides a direct visualization of the behaviour and thus facilitates the comparison of plant material as well as the classification of the effect of different environmental stresses in terms of the modifications it undergoes to adapt to new conditions (Strasser et al. 2000). **Figure 5** showed values from HWS-leaves at noon in the dry season relative to that of HS-leaves. Among the different parameters tested, we observed that PRI, Performance index (Pi_Abs) and leaf temperature (estimated as Δ leaf T $^{\circ}$, see methods) were affected by salt excretion, although to a different extent. The depletion of salt crystals in black mangrove leaves induced a decrease in the PRI and Pi_Abs, together with an increase in Δ leaf T $^{\circ}$, indicating that a possible function of salt deposition is to prevent leaves from overheating.

Discussion

Avicennia is one of the most salt-tolerant mangrove trees (Ball 1988). Its leaves are characterised by a high levels of salt excretion that enables it to maintain its mineral balance and water status under conditions of extreme salinity, thereby avoiding the accumulation of some ions (mainly chloride and sodium) that may have toxic effects at high concentrations (Hasegawa and Bressan 2000; Zhu 2001). Despite its extraordinary resistance and widespread distribution, there are only a few studies on the ecophysiological responses of this genus under natural conditions (Lin and Sternberg 1992; Gordon 1993; Sobrado and Ball 1999; Naidoo et al. 2010). In this study, we have set out to evaluate the potential gains that the accumulation of salt crystals on leaves confer on the plant in terms of photoprotection.

The leaves of several halophyte species follow a diurnal excretion pattern with a large reduction in excretion at midday (Ramadan 1998). This is also the case of the black mangrove in which higher salt secretion has been reported during the night (Gordon 1993; Naidoo 2010). However, as liquid excretion on the surface of leaves possesses a very high concentration of ions, precisely 96% of Na⁺ and Cl⁻ (Sobrado and Greaves 2000), salt deposition becomes only apparent after water evaporation. Thus, the accumulation of salt crystals is maximal during the day (usually at midday or early afternoon) when the extent of secretion is reduced (Ramadan 1998; Ramadan 2001) and is more conspicuous during the dry season (the authors' personal observation) when the air humidity drops and the daily accumulated radiation is higher (**Fig. 1**). Indeed, water stress conditions caused by the dryness of the atmosphere, greatly influence the efficiency of the excretion process (Ramadan 1998). These changes in climate conditions between both seasons are probably the causes for the changes in pigment composition (table 2) also. Thus, total VAZ/chl was higher in the dry season, indicating a higher demand for photoprotection as this parameter is usually proportional to the level of light stress to which leaves are exposed (Niinemets et al. 2003; Logan et al. 1996; Tausz et al. 2004). Interestingly, the content of α -tocopherol and γ -tocopherol also changed between seasons, the wet season being when γ -tocopherol increased significantly. This tocopherol has been reported to exert a specific function *in vivo* osmoprotection (Abbasi et al. 2007).

The accumulation of salt over the leaves of black mangrove alters the optical properties of leaves; in particular, it increases leaf reflectance in the blue and red regions of the spectrum (**Fig. 3**), thereby reducing the light absorbed by leaves. Thus, a mechanism to avoid the synergic and interactive effects of light excess and temperature, such as the decrease in light absorbance due to the increase in reflectance in salty leaves may be of special importance in the harsh tropical intertidal environment of the mangrove, where species usually become light saturated at 30–50% of full sunlight (Ball 1996).

As this process is reversible, the optical effects disappear once the salt is dissolved in water. A similar strategy of reversible reduction of leaf absorptance through the formation of salt crystals has been described in *Atriplex hymenelytra* in which higher reflectance also improves water use efficiency (Mooney et al. 1977). Mangrove trees often have low photosynthetic rates (Ball 1996); therefore, they must deal with excess absorption of sunlight to avoid the damage that can result from the overexcitation of the photosynthetic apparatus (Osmond 1994; Osmond et al. 1999). Several mechanisms that avoid photoinhibition by balancing light energy absorption and use have been described in mangrove trees. These include lower chlorophyll content

(Christian 2005), steeper leaf angles (Björkmann et al. 1988; Tuffers et al. 1999) and the activity of xanthophyll cycle pigments (Sobrado and Ball 1999; Christian 2005). Taking into consideration the evidence provided in the present study, the accumulation of salt in the black mangrove could be added to this list of strategies involved in the prevention of photo-oxidative damage. Indeed, the avoidance of high light intensities at midday (due to the accumulation of salt crystals) could give rise to better carbon gain. Data from **Figure 4** support this idea since, in the dry season, HS-leaves show higher photochemical efficiency during the afternoon than HW- leaves (**Fig. 4b**). The midday decrease in the efficiency of PSII shown by HWS was recovered shortly after predawn. Consequently, this may be understood as a protective downregulation in these exposed tissues, rather than as photodamage (Cheeseman et al. 1997; Sobrado 1999). Besides, HS-leaves showed a tendency to have higher values of PRI (table 1). This index was first formulated as an indicator of photosynthetic efficiency (Gamon et al. 1992), but it may also be a function of xanthophyll cycle de-epoxidation changes (Peguero-Pina et al. 2008; Nichol et al. 2012). Hence, coinciding with the driest and most light-stressing moment of each day, the reduction of light absorption due to salt accumulation improves the photochemical efficiency and performance (PRI) of black mangrove leaves (**Fig. 4** and Table 1).

The multiparametric description represented in **figure 5** summarizes what was happening in both types of leaves during the dry season. Pi_Abs encompasses fluorescence transient changes associated with changes in antenna conformation and fluctuations and is a practical index to use for studies of stress (Appenroth et al. 2001; Strasser et al. 2000) and physiological screenings (Strasser et al. 2000), this index being positively correlated with CO₂ assimilation rates (van Heerden et al. 2003) and for the assessment of tree quality (Hermans et al. 2003). As expected, the Pi_Abs of HS-leaves, on an equal chlorophyll (absorption) basis, was higher than HWS-leaves, indicating photosynthetic performance is low in these leaves due to a reduction in energy conservation from photons absorbed by PSII antenna, on the reduction of Q_B. Similar results were obtained in the same species exposed to high salinity stress, indicating that the main targets in PSII were affected by high salinity levels (Gonzalez-Mendoza et al. 2011).

The presence of salt crystals in leaves of *A. germinans* also had an influence on leaf temperature, as is shown by the significantly lower temperature in HS- compared to HWS-leaves (**Fig. 5**). A decrease in leaf temperature may enhance photosynthesis in mangrove species (Ball 1988), due mainly to the fact that under tropical conditions, the low transpiration rates of *Avicennia* are not enough to prevent leaves from heating above ambient temperature (Ball 1988). Thus, the salt in *A. germinans* leaves may not only represent a way to photoprotect leaves by reducing light absorption but also a way of protecting the leaves thermically, avoiding the

damaging effect of overheating. Therefore, although not essential for plant survival, the synergic and interactive effects of the simultaneous decrease in leaf temperature and light absorption add a new element to the overall photoprotective capacity of this species in harsh tropical intertidal environments.

Although the effect of other epicuticular structures and excretions such as hairs and waxes has been studied in greater depth (Morales et al. 2002; Sheperd and Griffiths 2006), only a few studies have focused on the effects of excreted salt crystals (Mooney et al. 1977, Naidoo et al. 2011). Although this strategy evolved primarily as a mechanism of salt tolerance, in the case of the salt excretion of *A. germinans*, its proven role in the prevention of photoinhibition and overheating fulfils the concept of “exaptation” (Gould and Vrba 1982): “features that now enhance fitness but were not built by natural selection for their current role”. Therefore, in the colonisation of seashores, this strategy may confer an advantage over plants, which despite excreting salt do not accumulate crystals on their leaf surfaces. Notwithstanding this daily and seasonal accumulation of salt, which enhances photoprotection in the black mangrove, it also represents one of the few examples of reversible photoprotective mechanisms among plants that function in conjunction with changes in photoprotective demand.

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Figure captions

Fig. 1 Meteorological conditions in Juan Venado Reserve during the course of one year (from November 2010 to November 2011): Daily quantum flux density (line) and daily mean temperature (open circles) (A) and daily mean relative humidity (open circles) and daily rainfall (line) (B).

Fig. 2 *Avicennia germinans* leaf. Note the salt excreted by the specialised glands on one half of the leaf. The salt on the other half has carefully removed with a tissue.

Fig. 3 Spectral Reflectance difference over 400-700 nm range for leaves of *A. germinans* with salt and without salt. Note that mean values of percentage of total reflectance and *p*-value with salt (Rs) and without salt (Rws) are indicated for the different ranges 400-500 nm; 501-600 nm; 601-700 nm. Values are means of 34 leaves \pm S.E.

Fig. 4 Photochemical efficiency in leaves of *A. germinans* with salt and without salt during a day course in August (wet season) and November (dry season). Asterisk indicates significant differences at $p < 0.05$ between the part with salt and the part without salt.

Fig. 5 A radar plot presentation of physiological parameters of *A. germinans* at noon in the dry season relative to that of leaves with salt: PRI, Δ leaf T° (increased leaf temperature calculated as the temperature difference between the adaxial and the abaxial sides), Reflec (% of total reflectance mean from 400-700 nm), V+A+Z (V-cycle pigments), PI_Abs (performance index on absorption basis) Vi (relative variable fluorescence at the I-step) and Vj (relative variable fluorescence at the I-step). The last three parameters are derived by the JIP-test from the fast rise (OJIP) transients. Values were normalized using as reference the corresponding values of non-salty leaves. Opened circles and closed circles indicate leaves with salt and without salt respectively.